

Obstetric Early Warning Scoring System

Alana McGolrick, MSN, RNC-OB, C-EFM — Dr. Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN, CEN — Dr. Lucy VanOtterloo PhD, RNC, CNS

Background & Significance

- Despite access to the world's leading healthcare, the United States has not made a significant impact on obstetric patient safety
- Imperative that a national agenda be developed to address incidence of unexpected maternal deaths
- Inaccurate assessment, misinterpretation of fetal and uterine activity, and late communication, led to either severe morbidity or maternal death
- Literature supports the need to develop an obstetric early warning system (EWS) to identify patients prior to worsening conditions

Purpose

The purpose of this Doctorate of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to:

- Develop an obstetric early warning system trigger tool for the intrapartum patient in the labor and delivery setting

The aim of this project was to:

- Identify the physiological parameters that indicate a potential emergent situation during the intrapartum stage

Methods

Setting

- Faith-based hospital in Orange County
- 5000 births annually
- 50 private labor and delivery rooms
- Magnet Designation

Sample

- Subject matter experts
- Hospital-employed labor and delivery registered nurses
- At least one year experience
- Certified in fetal monitoring and uterine activity assessment and interpretation

Plan-Do-Study-Act

(Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2015)

Data Collection

- Group discussions conducted at the hospital
- Subject matter experts (SME) volunteered to attend at least one of two initial review sessions
- Sessions were thirty (30) minutes in length
- A ten minute education segment presented to introduce OB Early Warning System (EWS)
- Self developed discussion guide utilized by the project leader to guide sessions
- OB EWS provided to the subject matter experts during sessions
- Notes taken during each session by the project leader
- Suggested SME edits and revisions were compared to the literature
- OB EWS revisions were completed if supported by the literature
- During the final session, the SME reviewed the OB EWS one additional time and approved the final format

Results

Discussion

Obstetric Early Warning System

- Includes most valuable physiological parameters per subject matter experts
- Determined vital sign priority order
- Important inclusion of urine output and level of consciousness as assessment data points to patient population
- Unique addition of fetal heart rate and uterine activity
- Removed quantification of blood loss due to inapplicability to intrapartum patient
- Color-coded per score severity stage to assist with recognition of patient's

Action Plan Algorithm

- Supports goal of early intervention and escalation of care
- Relevant terminology edits based on clinical setting
- Color-coded per stage of severity to assist with visual recognition of patient's status

Recommendations for Future Research

- National standardization of intrapartum physiological parameters
- Development of an electronic clinical decision support tool
- Implementation of pilot to test specificity and sensitivity of scoring system and action plan

Conclusion

- Project results support the necessity of an obstetric early warning system for the intrapartum patient
- Objective calculations of individual patient scores will initiate timely interventions, and escalation of care without treatment delays

References upon request
amgolrick@csu.fullerton.edu